

CONFLICT SITUATIONS IN THE STUDENT ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to conflict situations in the student environment, identifying their causes, the impact of these conflicts on the further development of interpersonal relations.

Introduction: Study loads, the acceleration of the pace of life, excessive psychological stress, environmental changes, physical inactivity, the development of technology and technology - all this affects the health of society, including the psychological health of students. Conflict situations in the student environment are now an inevitable and common occurrence, so we consider the study of this phenomenon an urgent problem that affects learning, academic performance, relationships between students and other aspects of a student's life.

Literature and methodology: The study was conducted at the Department of Public Health and Health Management of Samarkand State Medical University among 4th year students of the Faculty of Medicine. The sample consisted of 86 respondents, whose age ranged from 20 to 25 years. The gender composition was as follows: girls 58% and boys 42%. We have compiled a questionnaire, which consisted of 10 questions concerning the frequency of conflict situations among students, the attitude of students to conflicts, the gender of the initiators of conflicts, what is the cause of conflicts, the positive and negative sides of conflicts, the impact of conflicts on the further development of interpersonal relations in the group.

Results: To the question: "What is your attitude to conflicts?", the respondents answered in this way - negative (60%), indifferent (22%), positive (14%) and the rest (4%) - do not know. 17% consider themselves subjectively conflicting and 83% consider themselves non-conflicting. The results of the survey also showed that girls are the most frequent initiators of conflicts, and this is exactly what (88%) thinks, and this opinion is shared by respondents of both sexes. The majority of respondents (87.2%) do not believe that a scandal can be a solution to a problem between people, but the remaining 12.8% believe that this is a very acceptable method of solving problems and misunderstandings.

The most common causes of conflicts are: "stubbornness and unwillingness to give in to each other" (48%), "envy" (24%), "internal aggression" (13%), "desire to attract attention" (8%), "other" (7%).

A separate study group taken can serve as an indicator of the level of students' general conflict. So (38%) of students noted that, in their study group, conflicts occur "regularly", (24%) believe that "very often", (12%) indicated that conflicts occur: "very rarely", (26%) students noted that conflicts occur "rarely" in their study groups.

To the question: "Can you forgive your offender?" 87.4% answered that (YES) they can. In this regard, during the survey, the following question was asked: "Do you think that the presence of conflicts can have a positive effect on the development of intra-group relations?" The survey showed that 65% believe that conflict situations can positively influence the development of relations, 30% do not agree with this, and the remaining 5% find it difficult to answer. Therefore, in the course of the survey, the respondents were asked the following question: "Can trouble in everyday life affect students' conflict?" The results showed that 73% of the respondents believe that troubles in everyday life can influence the conflict of students, 25% answered that they cannot, and the remaining 2% of respondents find it difficult to answer.

It is not difficult to see that the level of conflict is very high. From the point of view of management, some conflicts are useful, as they help to identify a variety of points of view, provide additional information, and allow an analysis of relationships in the team. It makes the decision-making process of a group or leader more efficient, helps people express their thoughts and feelings, satisfy their needs for respect and power.

Discussions: Competent resolution of conflicts in the student environment can have positive consequences: conflict plays a huge role in shaping the character of the student's personality, and often contributes to team building. On the other hand, the negative consequences of conflicts in the educational environment often lead to psychological problems of group members.

Conclusion: Analysis of the study showed that various kinds of conflicts often arise in the student environment. They can take place both within the educational institution and outside it. Student conflicts are striking in their scale and diversity. The problem of conflicts in the student environment is very relevant, since their consequences are deterioration in academic performance, deterioration in psychological and physical health, the appearance of tension, anxiety, student self-doubt. The causes of conflicts are dealt with by psychologists, sociologists and other scientists. Insufficient knowledge of student conflicts requires further research in this direction.

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